

Determination of glucose in presence of urea

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Manuscript received 8 July 2002, revised 31 October 2003, accepted 26 August 2005

Abstract : Use of sodium metavanadate in refluxing dilute perchloric acid provides a new and efficient method for the determination of glucose in presence of urea.

Keywords : Glucose, urea.

Qualitative and quantitative methods for the determination of glucose samples have been reviewed recently¹. In this note we wish to report a method for the determination of glucose in the presence of urea. It is an attempt to develop simple methodology to determine glucose in biological fluids like blood and urine or in any other mixture of biological importance.

Results and discussion

Urea did not interfere in the determination of glucose and results are found to be extremely accurate. Advantages of the present method are : (i) very sharp and stable end point is obtained, (ii) the method is non-hazardous and (iii) a large number of determinations can be carried out simultaneously in a short time.

Experimental

Glucose (A.R.) and urea (Merck, G.R.) were dried under vacuum at 50°C for 8 h before use. Sodium metavanadate, perchloric acid (70%), potassium iodide and sodium thiosulphate (all Merck, G.R.) were used. Freshly prepared starch solution was used as indicator. Double distilled water was used throughout. Stock solu-

tion of sodium thiosulphate (0.1 N) was prepared and standardized iodometrically. 0.1 N metavanadate solution was prepared by dissolving sodium metavanadate (0.05 mol) in water. Cold aqueous solution of metavanadate was slowly added to perchloric acid (60%) with stirring. A golden yellow solution thus obtained was standardized iodometrically. 25.0 ml of vanadate solution was taken in a standard joint round bottomed flask (100 ml) and 2.0 ml of urea solution (0.5898 g dl⁻¹) was added to it and refluxed for 60 min over a low flame. The reaction mixture was cooled and titrated iodometrically. The above experiment was repeated with varying times of reflux and varying amounts of urea (including solid urea).

Standardization of vanadate by a standard solution of glucose :

Determination of glucose in presence of urea : 2.0 ml of a solution of glucose (0.9918 g dl⁻¹) was refluxed with 25.0 ml of vanadate solution for 60 min. The residual vanadate solution was titrated iodometrically. 2.0 ml of a solution of glucose of unknown strength and 2.0 ml of a solution of urea (unknown) were refluxed and titrated in the aforementioned manner. The results have been presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Analysis of a mixture of glucose and urea in solution

No. of Experiment	Volume of V ^V (ml)	Strength of glucose (g dl ⁻¹) (Taken)	Volume of glucose (ml)	Volume of urea (ml)	Strength of urea (g dl ⁻¹)	Volume of thiosulphate (ml)	Strength of glucose (g dl ⁻¹) (Found)	Error (±)%
1.	25.00	1.3158	2.00	-	-	7.60	1 3198	0 30
2.	25.00	1.0962	2.00	1.00	0.5882	9.50	1 0979	0 15
3.	25.00	0.9192	2.00	1.00	0 5882	11.10	0 9110	0 89
4.	25.00	1.5584	2.00	1.00	0.4286	5.80	1 5300	1.82

Table 2. Determination of glucose in a mixture with urea in the solid state

No. of Experiment	Volume of V ^V (ml)	Weight of solid glucose (g)	Weight of solid urea (g)	Volume of thiosulphate solution (ml)	Glucose (Found) (g)	Error (±)%
1.	25.00	–	–	19.00	–	–
2.	100.00	0.0990	0.0522	32.16	0.1009	1.20
3.	50.00	0.0326	0.0442	22.00	0.0328	0.60
4.	25.00	0.0278	0.0622	8.40	0.0271	0.28

Determination of glucose and urea in mixture which were taken in solid state :

Solid glucose (unknown amount) and solid urea (unknown amount) were added to a previously standardized vanadate solution and refluxed for 60 min. Residual vanadate was determined iodometrically. Results are presented in Table 2.

Formula for calculation :

If the volume of thiosulphate solution needed to titrate the residual vanadate after refluxing with an unknown solution of glucose is y ml, the volume of thiosulphate solution required to titrate the residual vanadate for a

known weight is x ml and if z ml of thiosulphate solution is required to titrate the volume of blank vanadate solution (used during reflux) the unknown amount of glucose (G).

$$G = W \frac{(z - y)}{(z - x)}$$

W = amount of glucose needed to standardize vanadate solution.

References

1. T. Tanaka, E. Shutto, T. Mizoguchi and K. Furushima, *Anal. Sci.*, 2001, 17, 277.